

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183227>

SOME PESTS OF VEGETABLE CROPS AND MEASURES TO FIGHT AGAINST THEM

Tuychiyeva Xilola Zokirjon qizi

Teacher of Fergana State University

Correspondence course

tuychiyevafdu1993@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

Since the climate of our republic is favorable in all respects, the cultivation of vegetable crops in agriculture is widespread. Vegetable products obtained from crops contain various substances necessary for the human body. This is because there are many vitamins, organic acids and trace elements an environmentally safe measure against various pests and diseases of crops - It is important to support events.

Key words: *Agriculture, rust mite, embossment nematode, tomato moth, spider mite, whitefly, onion fly, carrot fly, agrotechnical measures, control measures.*

Get a high and quality harvest in the cultivation of agricultural products one of the main factors is plant pests, diseases and weeds is to protect. A pest for obtaining environmentally friendly products from vegetables and integrated methods of disease control, especially agrotechnical and Great attention should be paid to biological control methods Rust and spider mite, bump nematode, white wing, tomato moth, the borer fly of tomatoes, including most vegetable crops are the main pests.

Rust mite affects plants belonging to the mite family (tomatoes, potatoes, ggplant and others) cause serious damage. It cannot be seen with the naked eye.

That is why rust mite in many cases causes damage with diseases replace Tomato fruit infected with rust mite is not suitable for consumption and the plant stops growing and developing. Leaf and plant sap damages the fruits. Leaves infected with it are silvery on the back shiny, and brown spots appear on the stems, and the top of the tomato fruit part cracks and hardens, and the leaves dry up.

In open and sheltered soils, the nematode of the bump is a vegetable, polyps and causes great damage to other agricultural crops. Root system of plants harms. Bumps appear on the root and completely cover the root system. The plant cannot get enough water and nutrients from the soil. As a result the plant dries up, the sun burns the fruits. Depending on the degree of soil damage 30-100% of the crop will die. Tomato moth.

A very dangerous pest that has spread in recent years is considered The larva penetrates the inside of the leaf and eats the tissue completely will graduate. It multiplies very quickly, gives 10-12 generations in one season. Kill the crop 100% does.

Cabbage juice. Cabbage sap is a two-year flowering alien in the egg stage in grasses, oviparous, larval and parthenogenetic female breeds have two-year flowering winters in weeds. Cabbage sap grows 16 times a year; in autumn, each female lays 2-4 wintering eggs. Mature stages and larvae settle in cabbage leaves and suck. As a result of their feeding, the leaves first become discolored, then the leaves turn slightly red it twists, changes and fades.

Cabbage white butterfly. Cabbage white butterfly is old in the bulbous stage hibernates in buildings, wall cracks, tree trunks and bushes. Females whose butterflies fly out in April-May are 250 each. They lay 300 eggs in heaps on cabbage leaves. Worms cabbage leaves It gnaws the leaves and leaves only the thick veins. Worms 15- For 30 days, the walls of abandoned buildings are fed on the trunks of trees and shrubs in the cracks, it passes into the dome. Cabbage white butterfly is 3-4 generations in the conditions of Uzbekistan develops by giving.

Onion fly. Onion fly damage to onions and garlic onions delivers Onions are planted with false bulbs at a depth of 10-20 cm winters in the fields. In early spring, flies fly to the plant in April-May lays 5-12 eggs on nearby soil fragments and onion leaves. When the larvae hatch from the eggs, they feed on the onions, and the onions rot. One 10-15 larvae develop in onions. The onion fly gives birth twice a year develops.

The carrot fly mainly affects carrots and other complex flowers will cause damage. Damaged tubers rot. False mushrooms are soil hibernates in the upper layers. Carrot fly 10-12 per plant, total It lays 100-1200 eggs. Carrot fly gives birth 2 times a year develops. Countermeasures. Agrotechnical measures: onions and garlic from onions open fields are plowed in deep autumn; in fields empty of onions plant residues are lost; onions should be planted early. Fresh carrots planting a crop 1.0 km away from the old crop field; autumn in the land plowing; thin out carrot seedlings.

Collecting plant residues in the fields where all the crops are planted will be lost; the land should be deeply plowed; 100 m weeds are destroyed in the radius.

Farmers and farmers, when using biological methods of pest control, to start breeding anti-mite encarsia in biolaboratories, micro sanctuaries to ensure the transfer of entomophages to cultivated crops it is necessary to organize and plant nectar-giving and seral plants

REFERENCES:

1. Khojaev Sh.T. "Integrated protection of plants from pests, and basics of agrotoxicology." Tashkent-2014. Page 225
2. Sh.T. Khojaev, E.A. Kholmuradov. Entomology, protection of agricultural crops making and the basics of agrotoxicology. Tashkent "Fan" publishing house-2009.
3. qizi Tuychiyeva, X. Z. (2023, January). Biologiya darslarida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning afzalliklari. In *international conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 378-380).
4. Tuychiyeva , X. Z. qizi, & Turdibekov, M. (2022). THE ECOSYSTEM OF INSECTS. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*, 1(19), 110–113. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/cf/article/view/715>
5. qizi Tuychiyeva, X. Z. (2023). TERMITLARNING BIOEKOLOGIYASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(27), 149-152.
6. Tuychiyeva, X. (2023). KERATOFAG HASHAROTLAR VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASHISH. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(12).
7. qizi Tuychiyeva, X. Z. (2023). KERATOFAG HASHAROTLAR VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASHISH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(4), 455-457.
8. Kamalova, H., & Tuychieva, H. (2021). Improving the spiritual immunological education of academic lyceum students specific issues. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(4), 616-620.